

The Wholly-Aromatic Thermotropic Liquid Crystalline Copolyesters and Their In-situ Composites

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ABSTRACT

It is well known that wholly-aromatic thermotropic liquid crystalline polymers (TLCPs) are new engineering plastics with unique properties. Due to TLCPs' property advantages such as mechanical, thermal resistance, radiation and chemical resistance, dimensional stability, they have been widely used in automobile, electron, aviation and aerospace industries. But because of their high processing conditions [1] and high prices, they have not gotten a rapid development. In this paper we present the synthesis of high molar mass liquid crystalline polymers (LCP), and by blending technique to obtain in-situ composites [2], in which the dispersed LCP phase is deformed into fibrillar form during processing, acting as a reinforcing phase. In order to obtain a good processing condition, their rheological properties have also been studied [3].

Keywords: in-situ composite, liquid crystalline copolyester, polysulfone, melt-blend

Experimental

Materials: 4,4'-diacetoxy bisphenyl (AC-BP)
P-acetoxy benzoic acid (AC-HBA)
Terephthalic acid (TPA)
M-phthalic acid (MPA)
4,4'-diacetoxy bisphenylmethane (AC-BPM)
Polysulfone (PSF)

Synthesis of Liquid Crystalline Polyesters

Put AC-HBA: AC-BP or AC-BPM: TPA: MPA = 1.2:0.4:0.28:0.12 (mol ratio) into a three-necked flask, added 0.001 mol $\text{Pb}(\text{AC})_2 + \text{Sb}_2\text{O}_3$ as catalyst. Draw the system into vacuum, stirred the reactants, heated them to 300°C gradually, got low molar mass LCP ($\text{MI} > 42$) (L-BP-LCP or L-BPM-LCP). Broke L-LCP into 20 mesh, then high molar mass LCP ($\text{MI} < 0.5$) (H-BP-LCP or H-BPM-LCP) could be obtained by solid state polymerization.

Preparation of in-situ Composites

Blended four kinds of LCP (high and low molar mass) with PSF, the LCP content was 2%,5%,10%,20%,30% respectively. Haake-Buchler was employed to obtain in-situ composites and some balance torque data. The shear stresses as a function of shear rates of these in-situ composites have also been investigated by XRL-400 capillary viscometry.

Results and Discussion

Structure and Properties of LCP

a. Textures of melted LCP

Fig.1 Polarized Optical Micrographs Taken of LCP at 380°C

Fig.1(a) shows the texture of H-BP-LCP, because H-BP-LCP have straight line diphenyl segments, they get high stiffness. Fig.1(b) is about H-BPM-LCP, which have bending bond $-\text{CH}_2-$ in their molecular, therefore they are not so hard. More and clearer thread-like textures are in pictures of H-BP-LCP can confirm H-BP-LCP have higher liquid crystallinity. We have also observed the low molar mass LCPs, the results showed that molar mass doesn't affect LCP's textures and liquid crystallinity.

b. Textures of LCP / PSF Blends

(a) H-BP-LCP / PSF

(b) H-BPM-LCP / PSF

Fig.2 Polarized Optical Micrographs Taken of LCP / PSF(10 / 90) at 340°C

Polarized optical micrographs of LCP / PSF are presented in Fig.2. There are many bright points in these pictures, shows that LCP can disperse in PSF matrix evenly. This is a premise condition for fibrous LCP to reinforce the matrix.

Effect of LCP's Structure, Molar mass and Content on the Rheology Properties of LCP / PSF Blends

Fig.3 Variation of balance Torque of LCP / PSF Melted Blends with LCP Content and Structure

a. Balance Torque of Melted Blends

Effect of LCP's structure and content on TQ of LCP / PSF melted blends are shown in fig.3. With increasing BP-LCP content the TQ of BP-LCP / PSF blends lowered. This is because BP segments have good liquid crystallinity and high stiffness, the BP-LCP domains can easily be oriented in the direction of flow. The oriented LCP domains smoothly glide past each other, thus lubri-

cating the polymer melt and lowering the melt viscosity of the blend, Especially when BP-LCP have high molar mass. So their TQ go down rapidly. But the TQ of BPM-LCP / PSF blends is increased with increasing BPM-LCP content, this is due to the bad liquid crystallinity of BPM-LCP.

b. Rheological Properties of melted Blends

In order to get the flow curves of different melted blends, we used capillary viscometry to determine their shear stresses and shear rates. From flow curves the values of non-newtonian flow index n were obtained, which were shown in Table.1.

Most of n values were less than 1, so these melted blends were pseudoplastic fluids. But these curves of blends containing higher L-LCP content were different, the curves could be grouped into two zones, two n values could be gotten from them, At low shear rate, L-Lcp can not stretch easily and are spherical shape (shown in fig. 4 (b)). These LCP spheres are difficult to glide past each other, so the blends are dilatant fluids, $n > 1$. With increasing shear rate, LCP spheres tend to form micro fibers, the blends become pseudoplastic fluids, $n < 1$.

Table.1 Non-Newtonian Flow Index n Values of Different LCP / PSF Melted Blends

LCP / PSF	2 / 98	5 / 95	10 / 90	20 / 80	30 / 70
H-BP-LCP / PSF	0.65	0.79	0.66	0.50	/
L-BP-LCP / PSF	0.70	0.80	0.86	5.44,0.40	/
H-BPM-LCP / PSF	0.64	0.68	0.85	/	0.84
L-BPM-LCP / PSF	0.42	0.79	0.72	/	1.57,0.66

Morphology of LCP / PSF In-situ Composites

Blended different LCP with PSF, extruded them into thin bars. Morphology of the fracture surfaces was examined via scanning electron microscopy (SEM). Shown in figs.4. From these figs., we can get following conclusions:

(a) H-BP-LCP / PSF = 10 / 90

(b) L-BP-LCP / PSF = 20 / 80

(c) *H-BP-LCP / PSF = 20 / 80*
(Skin Section)

(d) *H-BP-LCP / PSF = 20 / 80*
(Fracture Surface)

(e) *H-BPM-LCP / PSF = 30 / 70*

Fig.4 SEM Photomicrographs of Fracture Surfaces and Skin Sections of LCP / PSF Bars

a. LCP content must be high enough, or a little fibers can not reinforce the matrix effectively. See figs.4(a) and (c), (d).

b. From comparing figs.4(b) and (c), (d), we know that LCP molar mass is a key element in In-situ composites. The higher the LCP molar mass, the better.

c. LCP structure is important in forming In-situ composites. High stiffness segments can form micro fibers easily. Figs.4 (e) show that low stiffness H-BPM-LCP can not form fibrous structures even when its content is 30 percent.

References

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INTERFACES

